

Leadership Styles and Change Management in Higher Education

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In today's ever-evolving global landscape, the higher education sector has undergone unprecedented transformations. This dynamic necessitates universities to not only enhance cost efficiency but also to innovate in programme delivery. Indeed, in the case of Ireland, *The National Strategy for Higher Education* which set out a vision and national policy objectives for higher education in Ireland from 2011 to 2030 identified the following challenges that the Higher Education sector is facing: increased numbers of students entering the sector, the changing profile of students, increased unemployment and the changing nature of work, which have increased the emphasis on life-long learning and upskilling. However, while today's higher education leaders must be capable of managing change, there is limited research relating to this in a higher education setting. To fill the lacuna of research, this paper focuses on how effective leaders are at managing change in higher education and, by association, what leadership styles they use. It also examines the perceptions of staff concerning how well their leaders accept and manage change, and which leadership styles they consider most effective.

Key words: Leadership styles, Managing Change, Higher Education, Staff Perceptions

Three key highlights

- This paper argues that due to demands for increased cost efficiency and innovation in programme delivery, higher education leaders must be capable of managing the associated unprecedented changes.
- This paper highlights the numerous leadership styles available to higher education leaders to manage change, from more traditional leader-centred styles of transactional and transformational leadership to more modern shared leadership styles of distributed leadership.
- This paper concludes with the following two research questions:
 - What leadership styles do leaders use to manage change in universities and how effective are they?
 - What are the staff perceptions about how well their leaders manage change and which styles do they consider most effective?

Introduction

Higher education has experienced several drivers for change due to the global knowledge economy and increased public accountability (Marks and AL-Ali, 2022). The increased diversity of the student body and the greater corporatisation of higher education are also important drivers for change (Nair and Otaki, 2021). Within an Irish context, universities are expected to deal with increased student numbers, provide more flexible courses and be responsive to student needs and expectations (Joyce and O'Boyle, 2013). Higher Education institutions are increasingly expected to be more financially independent (Jones and Harvey, 2017). This has resulted in tensions among academics who feel their autonomy is being reduced and that, increasingly, managerialism is creeping in where the focus is on individual performance measures (Joyce and O'Boyle, 2013). The changing demands on higher education are changing traditional assumptions about the systems of management and leadership that should operate within universities (Joyce and O'Boyle, 2013). Although there is extensive research on leadership styles and their effectiveness in schools (Tian *et al.*, 2022), there is limited research on this area in higher education institutions. Some studies have focused on transformational leadership (Wang, 2022) and distributed leadership (Lizier, Brooks and Bizo, 2022) in higher education, but for the most part, the focus is on leadership within schools. There is also limited research on the change management capability of leaders in higher education. A recent study by Ezzedine *et al.*, (2023) examined the perceptions of staff in a medical and health sciences university in the Middle East and North Africa regarding the effectiveness of their leaders in managing change but this has not yet been replicated in an Irish context. This paper will examine the context in which universities operate, change management in higher education, leadership styles in higher education, and will conclude with important research questions that can fill the gaps within the literature.

The University Context

McMaster argues that some of the contradictions in universities are due to being hierarchical, 'collegial, loosely coupled, and organised anarchies' (2014, p. 434). Most of the academic work within universities is completed by committees. Usually, decisions are made by consensus and may require consideration by various committees before a decision is finalised. This is supported by McMaster (2014) who argues that her aforementioned tripartite description of Higher Education makes sense when viewed through the lens of academic work.

A collegial approach is also more suited to a changing environment. There are also different sub-cultures that exist across the university. Hofstede defines culture as: ‘the collective programming of the human mind that distinguishes the members of one human group from those of another. Culture in this sense is a system of collectively held values’ (1981, p. 24). Sub-cultures are cultural groups within a larger group who may hold differing beliefs or values from the larger group. In the university these sub-cultures exist in faculties, schools, research centres and in professional service areas (for example Human Resources, the Registry). These sub-cultures engage in different projects and activities. The power within these groups includes expertise power as well as legitimate power (French Jr and Raven, 1959). It is important for university leaders to consider these sub-cultures when trying to influence and when implementing change, and not always focus on influencing through the hierarchy.

A university on the east coast of Ireland is the context where it is anticipated this research will be conducted. This university has experienced several major change programmes in the last ten years, including a merger with several different institutions and a major digital transformation with the introduction of a new student information system. The author has undertaken various change management roles in this university.

Change Management in Higher Education

Change describes ‘any form of movement or transition from one state to another, from a common present to a future state’ (Fox-Wolfgramm, Boal and Hunt, 1998, p. 87). Due to the changing nature of higher education, organisations need to place change management at the centre of their strategy (Ezzeddine *et al.*, 2023). There are numerous models that organisations can use to manage change. These include the Kotter model of change that perceives change as a process (Kang *et al.*, 2022). There is also the Bridges model (developed by William Bridges in his book *Transitions: Making the Most of Change Transitions*) (Bridges and Bridges, 2017) which argues that change and transition are different. Change is external and situational and includes the new office, the new role, or the new policy. Transition is internal and is the psychological transition we go through to come to terms with the new situation. Bridges & Bridges (2017) argues that transitions are more difficult for people to cope with than changes. The Bridges model suggests that every transition consists of three phases: endings, the neutral zone, and new beginnings. Bridges outlines the various emotions that people experience during each of these phases and what leaders and managers can do to support staff through them.

There are also models that examine enablers of change such as the ADKAR model (Fry, 2021). ADKAR, developed by Hiatt (2006) is an acronym for five stages of change management. These include awareness, desire, knowledge, ability, and reinforcement. Leaders need to raise the awareness of employees of the need for change, motivate them to have a desire for change and highlight what they will gain from the change. Leaders need to identify what knowledge and skills are required to implement the change and give employees the opportunity to develop their abilities through practice. Finally, leaders need to find ways to make the change stick and measure whether employees are using the new system or reverting to their old way of doing things. Each of these models need to be adapted by leaders for use in complex organisations such as higher education. These models can form an important part of a leaders' toolkit in managing change. This study aims to examine the capability of leaders to manage change and the perceptions of their followers as to how capable their leaders are at managing change.

Griffith (2001, p. 298) in a paper called 'Why change management fails' claims that 'there is no such thing as successful change management.' One of the reasons for this is resistance to change (Erwin and Garman, 2010). Warrick (2023, p. 434) argues that 'resistance can be reasonable or unreasonable and can be expressed visibly or silently'. Leaders must be capable of managing resistance to change. De Biasi (2019) argues that a lot of change management approaches fail to consider the people side of things and their emotions (Buchanan, Claydon and Doyle, 1999). Therefore, if the people side of things are not addressed then organisational change will fail. During the change process employees must discard the old way of doing things and gradually adapt to the new by adjusting their behaviour (Bridges and Bridges, 2017). The organisation needs to focus on the process of transition and how this transition is led and managed (Bridges and Bridges, 2017). This is achieved by creating an organisational environment that is conducive to change by developing high levels of commitment to the change through creating a climate of trust, shaping the conditions, organisational institutions (systems, structures and principles) and incentives (de Biasi, 2019).

Leadership Styles within Higher Education

There are numerous leadership styles in operation in higher education. This section will explore three of these styles including transactional, transformational, and distributed leadership. The main leadership model within universities is the traditional hierarchy.

McMaster (2014) describes this as including clear lines of authority, a single supervisor and accountability and that this works better for professional staff and in times of complexity. In the university the governing authority and senior management team make decisions about how the university will operate. On the professional staff side there are line managers, supervisors, and clear lines of authority. The traditional hierarchy is often referred to as managerialism which is defined by Deem as a 'new discourse of management derived from the for-profit sector and introduced by governments into public sector institutions to reduce public-spending costs' (1998, p. 8). Transactional leadership is the leadership style strongly associated with it and is often portrayed as 'managerial leadership, which is strongly directive, motivating people with rewards in exchange for performance which meets expectations' (Joyce and O'Boyle, 2013, p. 71). The main business of the university is conducted on a day-to-day basis using transactional leadership. Staff are motivated by setting goals (through the performance management scheme) and expectations and rewards (for example salary) are given for satisfactory performance. The attempt to impose managerialism on the traditional academic culture has resulted in conflict among academics who wish to remain true to their values which go beyond box ticking and conforming to categories (Waitere *et al.*, 2011). Avolio (2010) suggests that transactional leadership can form the basis for transformational leadership, despite the differences in their orientations. If you honour your dealings and transactions with your followers, they will over time trust you.

Transformational leaders motivate others by raising their awareness about what the organisational goals are and by inspiring them to set aside their own needs for those of the organisation (Marks and Printy, 2003). From my experience effective transformational leaders have inspired others to follow them by sharing a vision, by empowering others to lead and by modelling the way. The full range of leadership model (Bass, 1998) comprises four styles of transformational leadership including charismatic leadership or idealised influence (leaders are admired and respected role models), inspirational motivation (leaders motivate their followers), intellectual stimulation (leaders develop new ideas for ways to do things) and individualised consideration (leaders focus on developing others). Bass (1998) argued that each leader demonstrated each of these styles most of the time. This model was developed from earlier work completed by Burns (1978) who differentiated between transactional and transformational leadership. Bass (1998) expanded on this work by arguing that leaders not only inspire their followers but also motivate both themselves and their followers. Tian *et al.* (2022) argues that from a theoretical point of view transformational leadership can help reduce

staff burnout because it focuses on staff needs, helps them pursue their goals, inspires them and highlights the importance of their work. Their study showed that transformational principal leadership helps reduce teachers job burnout. One of the criticisms of this is it relies too much on the transformational skills of the leader. Evers and Lakomski (1996) argue that the organisation should be focused on learning from its' mistakes by developing feedback loops. This links with the concept of double looped learning (Argyris, 1993). Rather than empowering a leader, the organisation becomes empowered thereby becoming a change agent.

A distributed leadership approach would appear to be a good fit for the university sector due to its history of both collaborative relationships and collegiality (Green and Ruutz, 2008). This approach includes leaders who are appointed to positions of authority and leaders who are recognised for their knowledge and expertise from different functions across the university. This includes both academic and professional leaders (Gronn, 2011), and stakeholders (Jones, Harvey and Lefoe, 2014b). Distributed leadership embraces both the notions of collegiality and autonomy and the need for management (Gosling, Bolden and Petrov, 2009). A distributed leadership approach can lead to sustainable outcomes as those involved champion the implementation of decisions to what they have been involved in or contributed to (Jones *et al.*, 2014a). This aligns with the change management approach of involving stakeholders in decisions that will affect them. The research shows that within change management teams, adopting a distributed leadership approach led to higher performance than the more traditional leadership approach (Pearce and Sims, 2002).

Conclusion

The university sector has experienced unprecedented change due to increased student numbers and the need to innovate programme delivery. Therefore, higher education leaders need to be able to manage change. There are numerous leadership styles that leaders can use to manage change including transactional, transformational, and distributed leadership. There is a lack of research about how leaders manage change in higher education. To fill this gap, this research aims to examine the following research questions: what leadership styles leaders use to manage change in universities and how effective are these styles. This research also aims to examine what are the staff perceptions about how well their leaders manage change and which styles they think would be most effective.

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